

LIMNOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD: JAPAN

Substantive editing in the land of the rising sun

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Thanks to the prevailing winds that carry moisture from the Sea of Japan and Pacific Ocean up over the mountains of Japan, this country receives abundant precipitation, which fills many rivers, lakes, and groundwater aquifers. These rich freshwater resources have nurtured lush ecosystems and facilitated development of Japan's culture and economy for thousands of years. On the other hand, intense precipitation events like typhoons harm Japanese people and society, and such events have been increasing in severity and intensity. For both the benefits and the harms, understanding the processes that control water resources has been well appreciated and Japan has a long tradition of hydrological studies; many important contributions here have been published.

Many SIL members are already familiar with Japanese hydrological sciences through cooperative research or participation in major international conferences in Japan (SIL in Kyoto in 1980, ASLO in Otsu in 2014, World Lake Conferences in Tsukuba in 1995 and 2018 and in Otsu in 1984 and 2001, among others). The International Lake Environment Committee Foundation, headquartered in Otsu, coordinates cooperation with many other international organizations and facilitates conferences, training and research. The Japanese government generously sponsors scholarships and fellowships to help foreigners study and conduct research in Japan.

In 1990, a few months after completing my first postdoc with Tom Berman at Kinneret Limnological Laboratory in Israel, I received one of these Japanese postdoctoral fellowships and moved to Japan to continue limnological research; in this postdoc with Takayoshi Kawai at the National Institute for Environmental Studies in Tsukuba, I used mass balances in mesocosms to study the ecology of Lake Kasumigaura. This postdoc was extended a few times until I landed a Foreign Professor position in biology at the University of Tsukuba, where I taught for 9 years. Along the way, my Japanese colleagues started asking me to polish up the language in their research manuscripts before submission to peer-reviewed journals. As the requests soon exceeded what I wanted to do myself, I made a side business and reached out on the internet to find skillful editors to farm the work out to. Little did I know that my little side business would steadily grow and I would quit my faculty position to run ELSS (my editing and translation company) full time and still be here doing it 30 years after I arrived in Japan!

Although my career objective was to be an aquatic ecology researcher, I have found other satisfying challenges and remain engaged in research through editing. In Japan and many other countries where English is not the native language, there is a great need for assistance to improve the clarity and cogency of the writing in research papers. The work is challenging and (usually) intellectually stimulating. The goal for each work request is to improve the writing such that the scientific story becomes easily understandable and convincing to readers. Good research writing goes beyond correct spelling and grammar; effective editors must wrap their minds around the story as a whole and find ways to smooth the reader's path to understanding. Although substantive editing is not peer review, good substantive editing overlaps

with peer review and the best editors propose ideas that improve the science.

Although startup businesses are often risky, I reduced risk by operating ELSS in parallel with my academic career for about 10 years until incorporating. When the business started in the mid-90's, there were few companies in the market. As research has become more international, the language services marketplace has grown and become more competitive. My biggest challenge has been finding freelance editors who meet our high standards. A doctorate and research experience are useful, but not reliable indicators of the full package of substantive editing skills.

Good substantive editing requires proficiency in a wide range of skills. The results of editing are always best when the editor has deep knowledge of the research field of the paper being edited, which facilitates reading between the lines. Beyond intelligence and skillful writing, other important traits of editors are attention to detail, conscientiousness, and some perfectionism. Speed is not necessarily important for agencies or clients, but as pay is usually by the word, speed improves pay/time. Perhaps most important, effective editors are good at putting themselves in the shoes of the readers, who are the ultimate target of the paper. Although authors' or their institutions pay for the work, the ultimate client is the reader.

What kind of people are ELSS freelance editors? Some are retired academics who enjoy the cognitive challenges of substantive editing. Some are parents who appreciate flexibility in work schedules. Freelancing has advantages over more traditional work situations; freelancers can adjust the amount of work they accept and work from home (useful during a pandemic) or while traveling. Disadvantages usually include the lack of health and other social insurance. The flow of work is variable, but skillful editors usually can get as much work as they want and retain the right to refuse offered papers. As boss, I work hard, but every winter I look forward to sliding down that ample Japanese precipitation in some of Japan's many world class ski areas. Contact me if you'd like to tackle the challenges of substantive editing or skiing Japanese mountains.

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ELSS, Inc. improves the quality and publication success of research writing and other technical communication through teaching, consulting, and provision of high-quality editing, dictation, and translation services. ELSS is a reliable, trustworthy, and responsive service provider and partner for its customers, and a pleasant, fair, and honest employer for its employees and subcontractors.

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A traditional Hobikisen fishing boat - Lake Kasumigaura, Japan. Photo by Rick Weisburd.